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Rural Development: A Strategy for the Reduction of Rural-Urban Migration in Essien Udim Local Government Area

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Abstract

This study is an examination of rural development as a strategy for the reduction of rural-urban migration in Essien Udim local government area of Akwa Ibom state. Related literature were reviewed, and the Bright Light Theory and the Human Capital Theory were used as the theoretical framework. The study adopted a survey research design. Purposive and snowball sampling techniques were also adopted for the study. Data were collected from both primary and secondary sources, and 225 respondents were sampled in the course of the study. The data generated from the field of this study was analysed using frequency tables and simple percentages. Findings from the study revealed that access to infrastructure, education and industries will bring absentee and diasporic indigenes of Essien Udim local government area back home; there have been effort by government agencies and NGOs to develop the rural areas but such effort has not been sustainable and has not yielded any positive result; the presence of infrastructure will create employment to the youths, make businesses to thrive and reduce rural-urban migration; rural dwellers will compete favourably with those in the urban areas if there is a conscious effort in the development of the rural areas; and continuation of rural development plans, adoption and implementation of town planning laws can beautify the rural areas. The study recommends that local, state, and federal governments should ensure the full participation of members of rural communities and grassroots organisations in the design and implementation of rural development policies and programmes.

Keywords: Rural Development, Rural-Urban Migration, Strategy

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Introduction

The growth of the world population as at 2020 stood at 7.9 billion. The average population is estimated at 81 million per year, and the world population is projected to reach 10 billion in 2057 (United States Census Bureau, 2012; World Population Clock, 2021). According to the United Nations Department of Social and Economic Affairs (2018), about 4.2 billion people, or 55% of the world population, live in urban areas, which is expected to increase to 68% by 2050. Although there has been barely a reduction in the population over the years, if the trend continues, the negative impact of this will be increased demand for food, water, housing, energy, healthcare (increase in maternal and child mortality), transportation, and the general cost of living.

In Africa, population growth seems not to be different, as the current population stands at 1.3 billion, which is equivalent to 16.72% of the total world population. Africa ranks 2nd among the regions of the world ordered by population, and 43.8% of the population lives in urban areas (Worldometer, 2021; UNDESA, 2018). However, the current population of West Africa stands at 415 million, which is equivalent to 5.16% of the total world population, and 4.77% of the population lives in urban areas (Worldometer, 2021; UNDESA, 2019). However, because of the large and increasing population size, the number of people added to the global population will remain high for several decades, which may be the product or outcome of migration and a lack of meaningful industrialization and infrastructural development. In Nigeria, the case seems not to be different, as the total population in 2016 stood at 193,392 million, and as of 2021, it increased to 213,327 million (National Bureau of Statistics, 2018; Worldometer, 2021). Nigeria's population is equivalent to 2.64% of the total world population, while the country is ranked number seven in the list of countries according to population growth. 107 million people, or 52.0% of the population in Nigeria, live in urban areas as at 2020 (UNDESA, 2018; NBS, 2018). It has been estimated that between 2000 and 2030, nearly 100% of this annual growth will occur in the less developed countries in Africa, Asia, and Latin America, whose population growth rates are much higher than those of more developed countries (Oramah, 2006; US Census Bureau, 2005). Moreover, projections also show that urbanisation, the shift in the human population from rural to urban areas combined with the overall growth of the world's population, could add another 2.5 billion people to urban areas by 2050, with about 90% of this increase taking place in Asia and Africa (UNDESA, 2018).

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In recent times, rural development as a strategy has been played down in budgeting, planning, policies, and programmes, with an increasing burden on the urban areas in attending to amenities, infrastructure, and other social, economic, and environmental challenges in Nigeria. Development is a multidimensional process because it covers many aspects of life, such as sociopolitical, economic, and psychological. According to Umebau (2008), rural development is a process whereby efforts are made in order to facilitate a significant increase in resource productivity with the central objective of enhancing rural income and increasing employment opportunities in rural communities for rural dwellers to remain in the area. The greater the increase in urban centres, the higher the cost of living and the lower the quality of life among urban dwellers. Therefore, developing rural areas may act as a strategy for population redistribution between rural and urban areas.

Consequently, the gap between urban and rural areas is very wide in terms of economic development, quality of life, access to opportunities, facilities, amenities, and the general standard of living. This leads to what is characterised as the rural-urban dichotomy (Mammud, 2019).

Some rural areas are grossly neglected as far as development projects and programmes are concerned. Yet, rural areas are the producers of industrial raw materials and guarantee food security. As a result of the relative underdevelopment of rural areas when compared with urban areas, rural areas are usually characterised by a high propensity for outmigration because of the lack of infrastructure that would have made life meaningful for the populace.

The different rural development policies in Nigeria have shown that the area is critical to the development process. This is because the development process attracts huge financial and material resources employed to improve the living conditions in rural areas with a view to curbing the streaming rural-urban migration. However, Onuorah (2006) posits that the lofty objectives, policies, and government initiatives towards developing rural areas never endured beyond the government that initiated the schemes. The development of rural areas constitutes an important sector in the nation's economy at both the micro and macro levels and can reduce the population of urban areas. As revealed by Umebali (2006), a greater percentage of the total population lives in urban areas, while the majority of those who live in rural areas are engaged in agriculture. If we must make rural areas attractive to live in and reduce the population in urban areas, then

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meaningful efforts geared towards sustainable rural development must be aggressively and vigorously pursued. This is seen as the main phobia that has often pushed people to migrate from rural areas to urban areas because of the perceived opportunities in urban areas.

However, it is apparent from the forgoing that, given the importance of the rural areas towards developing the national economy, enhancing the development of the rural areas should be central to government. Regrettably, these rural sectors of Nigeria, vital to the socioeconomic development of the nation, have been neglected in the distribution and establishment of projects and programmes. Therefore, giving attention to rural areas through massive infrastructural development, social amenities, government establishments, and private sector investment would attract retirees and former migrants to the rural areas to spend the rest of their lives. On the strength of this, we are of the opinion that a thorough investigation of the extent of rural development and its influence on migrants' intentions to return to the countryside would reveal other hidden truths about the development of Essien Udim local government area.

Statement of the Problem

Rural development is increasingly becoming a great concern to the different tiers of government. Although different rural development programmes have been introduced by successive governments in Nigeria with huge material and financial resources expended on them, not much is there to show for it. Beyond this, such policies have often died with the government that initiated them without any impact being felt by rural dwellers. In this regard, Abiona (2006) contended that there is usually the absence of sustained, comprehensive, and conclusive implementation of rural development policies in Nigeria.

In order not to create confusion, there have always been erroneous misconceptions by successive governments that rural development is synonymous with agricultural development, a notion that was unable to stand the test of time in view of several agricultural development programmes embarked upon by successive governments in Nigeria. Also, such development indices and physical presence, such as socioeconomic amenities like schools, hospitals, recreational facilities, a good road network, electricity and pipe-borne water, loans, and other incentives that are capable of transforming rural communities and eventually making them attractive for habitation,

were and are still lacking or inadequate. Beyond this, several of these programmes were initiated from the top to the bottom as contracts for the party and political bigwigs. Thus, it excluded the supposed beneficiaries (the rural people).

Consequently, the gains of being trained as experts in development, managers of resources, personnel for the utilisation of rural key inputs in rural development, and partners in progress had eluded the rural people, thereby sustaining the rural landscape as an underdeveloped segment of society. In this regard, the absence of a good road network, electricity, social amenities, educational, health, and socioeconomic infrastructure, and investments in government establishments were lacking, the resultant effect being the constant flight of young people or brain drain to more socio-economically active centres for human dignity, welfare, and development. The tendency for the return of indigenes in diaspora under this guise has always been a mirage.

In light of this, meaningful rural development practices through policies and programmes within and outside could illuminate the landscape of rural settlements and cause many sons and daughters in diaspora to return, invest, and make their settlements nodes of development and opportunities. Hinged on the strength of this, we feel that an investigation into the various strategies for rural development could reveal more than it is known.

Objectives of the Study

- i. Examine how effective rural development can bring back absentee indigenes of Essien Udim Local Government Area.
- ii. Examine the potency of infrastructural development in attracting diaspora indigenes back to rural Essien Udim Local Government Area.

The following research questions will guide the study:

- i. How effective can rural development be in bringing back indigenes in diaspora to the rural villages in Essien Udim Local Government Area?
- ii. What is the potency of infrastructural development in attracting the diaspora indigenes back to rural Essien Udim Local Government Area?

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Review of Related Literature and Theoretical Framework Effective Rural Development as an Attraction for Migration Concepts of rural development

The concept of rural development is very wide, and it is a multidimensional process that covers areas such as agriculture, health education, the provision of rural infrastructure, social life, political and economic issues, as well as commerce and industry and their integration with the national economy. Since the concept of rural development is very broad, it is always assumed by policymakers that rural development is synonymous with agriculture. To correct this impression, it is very necessary to provide a detailed definition of the concept. Thus, according to the United Nations;

... The concept of integrated rural development implies that it is a composite or comprehensive programme for rural development in which all relevant sectors such as agriculture, education, housing, healthcare and employment are conceived as interlinking elements in a system having horizontal as well as vertical linkage in operational and spatial terms (1976:4).

According to Aziz (1999), rural development is a complex process that involves the interaction of economic, social, political, cultural, technological, and other situational factors. Hence, for the actualization of rural development, these factors have to be integrated with local government policies and plans with the objective of improving the quality of life of the people in the rural sector. In the words of Mabogunje (1981), rural development is concerned with the self-sustaining improvement of rural areas and implies a broad-based re-organisation and mobilisation of the rural masses so as to enhance their capacity to cope effectively with the daily tasks of their lives and with the changes consequent upon such. Moreso, rural development is important not only for its impact on rural places and people but also for its contribution to the overall development of the nation (Gana, 1996). In the Nigerian experience, where the bulk of the people and land are rural and where the level of rural output is very low because of a lack of industrialization, rural mobilisation provides the quickest and most direct route to national development. However, this will require the adoption of appropriate

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technology, which will reduce rural-urban migration and also raise rural productivity and efficient utilisation of resources; the creation of an efficient transport network for rural and urban areas to ensure easy transportation of agricultural produce for massive food production; and the supply of industrial raw materials.

Furthermore, Diejomah (1973) is of the view that rural development is the process of increasing the level of living of the rural population, measured by food and nutrition level, health, education, housing, recreation, and security. Corroborating this, Adegboye (2013) posits that rural development is the development of the rural people in a continuous manner so as to enable them to most effectively and efficiently utilise their intellect, technology, and other resources for further development of both themselves and their resources. Uwakah (1995) sees rural development as a change process that involves moving the rural people from what is to what ought to be.

Moreover, Malcom (2003) referred to rural development as the process of improving the quality of life and economic well-being of people living in relatively isolated and sparsely populated areas. According to Alanana (2005), rural development could be regarded as a process in which a set of technological, sociocultural, and institutional measures are implemented with or for the inhabitants of rural areas with the aim of improving their socio-economic status or living conditions to achieve a balance between the local and national sectors. Idris (2011) views rural development as a continued set of actions by government agencies, non-governmental organisations, and the rural populace to improve the rural conditions of the rural people, a process that leads to a series of changes within the confines of a given rural setting that eventually will result in the improvement in the general living conditions of the rural dwellers.

Other studies by Muagbalu (1992), Idike (1991), Offiong (1980), Ake (1980), Ujo (1994), and Akpan (2012) also agreed with the above definition but explained more in details. Apparently, it is observed that the ambit of rural development is very wide and that it requires a comprehensive approach. It includes the generation of new employment, more equitable access to arable land, equitable distribution of resources, widespread improvements in health, nutrition and housing, and the creation of incentives and opportunities. It also involves the ability of the local government to create wider opportunities for individuals to realise their full potential through education and sharing in the decisions and actions that affect their lives.

Infrastructural development and the return of migrants

Nigeria has adopted several strategies towards improving the well-being of rural dwellers and also bring those who are in urban areas back home. This is because rural transformation is a necessary foundation for social and economic progress. These strategies include:

Community development as a strategy for rural development

Community development is designed to promote better living for the whole community with the active participation and initiative of the people. It works mostly through the organisation of personal help, cooperative efforts on the part of the community, and technical assistance from the government and NGOs. The emphasis of community development is on group action in improving rural conditions, and the welfare of the group supersedes the welfare of the individual.

This is also a combination of community and government efforts towards improving their economic, social, and cultural conditions; it is not concerned with one aspect of life such as agriculture, business, health, or education, and people work together to shape their future. The effectiveness of a community development strategy depends on the extent to which the government encourages local planning and participation.

Agricultural extension practice and rural development

Agricultural extension is the education of the farming community on ways of raising their standard of living. It grew out of the need to extend the benefits of new knowledge, facts, and ideas arising out of intensive research to all people. According to Uwakah (1995), extension is a science that deals with the creation, transmission, and application of knowledge designed to bring about planned changes in the behaviour complex of people with a view to helping them to live a better life through learning new ways of improving their vocation, enterprise, and institutions. Agricultural Extension concentrates on the development of agriculture as the economic foundation for rural progress, but it is also indirectly concerned with other rural problems such as health, nutrition, and cooperatives with other agencies directly responsible for promoting and facilitating these services, which are not exclusively agriculture. The success of this approach depends on the competence and morale of the staff as well as taking the

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farmers into confidence. The effectiveness of an extension programme is measured by its ability to change a static situation into a dynamic one.

Integrated rural development

Integrated rural development is the best solution to the challenges facing rural areas in Nigeria. It is based on the understanding that a combination of factors—not only the right technology and education but also access to physical inputs, an attractive market, and the provision of infrastructure—are essential to reducing the population of urban areas, causing people to migrate to rural areas. It is a multidimensional approach in which programmes of agriculture, education, health, rural electrification, and cooperatives are considered to be related to each other rather than treated in isolation. This approach is integral because all of its components are important and appreciated for the part they play, both individual and collective. The major objective of this approach is the mobilisation of human and material resources for the creation of a healthy national economy whose benefits will be fairly distributed among all the rural people (Anaeto, 2003).

Co-ordinate rural development

Co-ordinate rural development involves the efforts of universities to partner with their host communities to bring solutions to the challenges of rural development; it is also in line with the integrated rural development strategy. It involves the responsibility of universities to extend practical knowledge acquired from research to solve the problems of the surrounding rural communities.

Concept of population turn-around

Rural-urban migration is one of the most distressing problems affecting the socioeconomic development of rural areas in Nigeria. This is a situation where the desire for better employment, business opportunities, and education pushes both active young and old people out of the rural areas to the urban areas.

Historically, migration existed internally across city boundaries to enable excess labour to be taken slowly from the rural areas to provide a workforce for industries in the urban areas and therefore aid industrialization and economic growth (Ijere, 1981). However, over time, the rate of rural-urban migration has rapidly outweighed the rate of

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job creation in developing and underdeveloped countries with overstretched social and infrastructural amenities in urban areas. Rural-urban migration may be occasioned by voluntary or involuntary forces. Involuntary or forced migration takes place when migrants have no choice on whether to move or not, while voluntary migration is done by choice (Lykke, 2002). Gimba & Kumshe (2012) posit that discriminatory government policies in favour of urban development in response to disparities in income, employment, and other socioeconomic amenities available within the urban and rural areas being privileged are the consequences of rural-urban migration. Others related it to spontaneous, emotional, structural, traditional, and some other factors. Corroborating this, Adewole (2012) reveals that various factors could predispose a certain rural population to migration, which might be due to crises, ethno-religious conflicts, and wars. In a study carried out by Agyemang (2013), he summarised the major causes of rural-urban migration in Nigeria. He noted that different motives account for rural-urban migration among rural dwellers in Nigeria, which include sociocultural issues where people are forced to migrate to avoid numerous social problems at their places of origin; poor infrastructural development and a lack of basic social amenities; the search for better economic opportunities such as jobs; accessibility and ease of communication and transportation; and the extension of the road network from major towns to the peripheral urban and rural areas, which resulted in a decrease in transportation costs and improved communication systems.

Moreso, the negative effects of rural-urban migration are enormous, as rural areas are mostly disabled at various levels by inaccessibility, seclusion, underdevelopment, extreme poverty, ignorance, depopulation, hunger, and all types of incapacity. Coupled with these is the fact that migration from rural to urban areas leads to a reduction in the number of rural populations, a negative effect on rural agricultural output, and a slowed pace of development in rural areas (Ekong, 2010). With the exit of youths and young adults from the villages and rural communities, the aged, women, and children are left behind to labour on the farms, which leads to a reduction in agricultural output with its attendant effect on the gross domestic product of the nation, lowered funds for development, income, and standard of living of rural inhabitants, underdevelopment, and total desertion of the areas (Adejugbe, 2004). The constant reduction in rural population over the years will invariably lead to gross rural neglect by the government, as they tend to concentrate on developing the more obviously

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populated urban areas (McCarthy, 2004). Corroborating this, Badru (2004) opined that this further reinforces the vicious cycle of gross rural neglect and underdevelopment, as reflected in the lack of rural industrialization and poor physical, social, and institutional infrastructure. Also, Lykke (2002) opined that rural-urban migration makes the highly educated and most agile people migrate from rural to urban areas, leaving behind the feeble and uneducated people who are not able to combat poverty successfully, which in turn increases the differences in the standards of living of the rural and urban inhabitants.

Moreover, Lykke (2002), McCarthy (2004), Adejugbe (2004), Badru (2004), Uma, Eboh & Obidike (2013), and Eliss & Harris (2004) have stated that the incessant drift of the rural populace to urban areas has led to social, economic, environmental, physical, and other severe problems such as congestion in urban centres with attendant consequences such as the spread of communicable diseases, overstretched social amenities, motorable roads, pipe-borne water, and housing. Other consequences of rural-urban migration include urban traffic congestion, unemployment, a high crime rate such as advance fee fraud, political and civil unrest, armed robbery, alcoholism, drug abuse, prostitution, hooliganism, health hazards from pollution, air, water, and noise, inadequate refuse and sewage disposal systems, poor drainage systems resulting in flooding, the growth of slums leading to shanty settlements, cultural changes, juvenile delinquency, and an overall decline in traditional values.

Consequently, rural-urban migration could be reduced with the involvement of rural communities and rural beneficiaries of rural development projects at all stages or phases of the project (Ocheni & Nwankwo, 2012). The people's contributions in the form of ideas, financial resources, and human resources will serve as a motivating factor for them to see to the complete success of the programme, and since the rural dwellers know and understand their environment and conditions better than the policy formulators and decision makers who operate from outside, it is better to involve them in rural development programmes. Gana (1996) notes that in the developed world, policymakers explore all possible options and adopt inclusive practices in rural development policies, and where appropriate institutional frameworks are put in place to strengthen and ensure rapid realisation of rural development goals, the trend in rural-urban migration and rural underdevelopment has been stemmed. Corroborating this, Aziz (1976) notes that in the developed world, government is seen and viewed as a continuum; rural development projects are not abandoned. Moreover, rural

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development is significant to combating rural-urban migration in Nigeria, and it is capable of changing the ways through which we manage the rural areas, which will make a difference in governance practices in Nigeria.

Challenges of rural development

The challenges threatening rural development, especially in developing countries, are numerous and cut across different sectors of the economy. Most often, rural development policies and programmes are discontinued whenever there is a change in government leadership. Most times, a new government abandons the projects and programmes of its predecessor, even when such programmes are appropriate. In this regard, Ajadi (2010) noted that there is usually the absence of sustained, comprehensive, and conclusive implementation of rural development programmes. Rural development programmes are not well implemented, and the targeted population, which are the rural dwellers, hardly benefit as some of the funds meant for projects are diverted, which truncates the development process of the rural areas (Ekong, 2010).

Moreover, successive governments in Nigeria over the years have made attempts at enhancing rural development through various programmes and policies, but its meaningful realisation has remained a mirage. This is clearly seen in the lack of basic amenities and the glaringly low standard of living conditions among the rural populace (Ugwuanyi & Chukwuemeka, 2013). One major effect of this rural underdevelopment is rural-urban migration, which is rapidly reducing the active population that constitutes the workforce of the rural areas in Nigeria. In recent times, there has been a noticeable high level of rural-urban migration in search of better standards of living and bigger opportunities for meaningful economic and social life (Oghoghouje & Jerry-Eze, 2011). This is dysfunctional, not only for rural development but also for overall national development.

However, according to Haruna (2000), Alanana (2005), and Ekong (2010), rural development programmes have failed because they flow from top to bottom, excluding rural people. In other words, the programmes are formulated and implemented by government officials in league with foreign interests to the neglect of the peasant producers who are knowledgeable in the process of rural production. Consequently, due to the non-involvement of rural producers in the process of their development, these development programmes do not record the desired success. The point of argument here

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is that the interests of those who control the machinery of government do not often confirm those of the rural poor. As a result, the various attempts aimed at transforming rural areas have failed to yield positive results. The failure of most rural development programmes can be attributed to the glaring contradictions in the activities of the government saddled with the responsibility of implementing the programmes and the inability to reconcile the interests and needs of the local people (Ekong, 2010). This continues with the persistent problem of poverty, lack of infrastructure, and rural-urban migration in rural communities in Nigeria, which constitutes a barrier to rural development. Rural development can only achieve success when the people are willing to accept and participate in initiating and implementing the policies and programmes of the government.

Moreso, corruption and mismanagement of resources at different levels of government in Nigeria also hindered the effective utilisation that would have been channelled towards developing the rural areas (Ekong, 2010). The Transparency International Index ranked Nigeria as the 149th least corrupt nation out of 180 countries in 2020, with an average of 121.48% from 1996 until 2018 and 25% in 2020 (Corruption Perception Index, 2020; Udom, 2021; Adelabu, Mwangi, & Ndiiri, 2018). Recently, the rural area has been propelled by increasing famine, desertification, loss of grazing settlements, inter and intra-tribal conflict, as well as farmer and herder conflicts, which have led to the loss of lives and properties and produced several internally displaced persons (IDPs), which further impoverished the people (Jega, 2011). The overall consequence of these challenges on rural dwellers is the absence of good road networks, electricity, quality healthcare, quality education, economic infrastructure, and a lack of government establishments, which causes the constant rural-urban migration of young people and brain drain in search of livelihood, economic activities, and development.

Theoretical Framework

Bright-Light Theory

Historically, migration has been a way of life in Africa, and African people have migrated in response to demographic, economic, political, and other factors, including environmental disasters and conflicts. The bright light theory suggests that people migrate from rural areas to urban areas because of one of two general causes: overpopulation and environmental deterioration in the rural areas (the push factor) or

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the allurement or attraction of the city (the pull factor, or the so-called bright-light theory). The hallmark of the bright light theory of migration is that rural to urban migrants tend to be attracted by new facilities in urban areas, which is a result of persistent underdevelopment in the communities of origin of the migrants (Arthur, 1991). The bright-light theory was developed by Ernest Ravenstein in 1889. Ravenstein, an English geographer, used census data from England and Wales to develop his "Laws of Migration." He concluded that migration was governed by a "push-pull" process: unfavourable conditions in one place (oppressive laws and heavy taxation) "push" people out, and favourable conditions in an external location "pull" them out.

Moreover, Ravenstein's bright-light theory states that the primary cause of migration was better external economic opportunities. In this theory, it is believed that the volume of migration decreases as distance increases; migration occurs in stages instead of one long move; population movements are bilateral; and migration differentials such as gender, social class, and age influence a person's mobility (Byerlee, 1974).

Although several theories have agreed with Ravenstein's bright light theory, the dominant theories in contemporary scholarship are more or less variations of his conclusions. According to Lee (1966), the bright-light theory should give more emphasis to internal or push factors. He argues that variables such as distance, physical and political barriers, and having dependents can impede or even prevent migration. The migration process is selective because differentials such as age, gender, and social class affect how people respond to push-pull factors, and these conditions also shape their ability to overcome intervening obstacles (Arthur, 1991). Furthermore, personal factors such as a person's education, knowledge of a potential receiver population, family ties, and the like can facilitate or retard migration.

Methodology

This study favours the descriptive survey research design owing to the need to work with information provided by research participants. The purposive and snowball sampling techniques were used to select two hundred and twenty-five (225) respondents selected from indigenes and non-indigenes of Essien Udim LGA, including traditional leaders, political leaders, religious leaders, youths, and returnees, which include civil servants, teachers, bankers, military personnel, and business owners—all retired. The Taro

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Yamane method of sample size determination was used to determine the sample size. Data were collected through the administration of a structured questionnaire and analysed using simple percentages (%). The Cronbach (1951) Alpha Statistical test was used to test the reliability coefficient, and the result showed 0.65%, which indicates that there was a high degree of internal consistency.

Results, Findings and Discussion

Research Question 1

How effective can rural development be in bringing back indigenes in diaspora to the rural villages in Essien Udim Local Government Area?

Table 1: Effectiveness of rural development in bringing back absentee indigenes in diaspora

S/N	QUESTIONS	SA	A	D	SD
1.	Will you say that access to infrastructure, education and industries will bring indigenes in the diaspora back home?	200 (88.8%)	150 (66.6%)	80 (35.5%)	55 (24.4%)
2.	Will you say you are living the kind of life people in the urban areas are living?	170 (75.5%)	110 (48.8%)	195 (86.6%)	220 (97.7%)
3.	Are you comfortable with the current state of your community?	99 (44%)	59 (26.22%)	210 (93.3%)	219 (97.33%)
4.	Has there been any effort by the government and NGOs to improve infrastructure in your area.	199 (88.4%)	169 (75.1%)	88 (39.1%)	153 (68%)

Source: Researcher's fieldwork, 2023

Table 1 shows the opinions of respondents on the effectiveness of rural development in bringing back absentee indigenes in diaspora. It can be observed that the majority of the study respondents, 200 (88.8%), strongly agreed that access to infrastructure, education, and industries will bring indigenes in the diaspora back home, as compared to 150 (66.6%) who agreed to this fact. On the other hand, 80 (35.5%) and 55 (24.4%) disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively. This implies that access to infrastructure, education, and industries will bring indigenes in the diaspora back home. The majority of the respondents, 220 (97.7%), strongly disagreed that they are living the kind of life people in urban areas are living, while 195 (86.6%) disagreed with this

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assertion. Whereas, 170 (75.5%) and 110 (48.8%) of the study participants strongly agreed and agreed that they are living the kind of life people in urban areas are living. This implies that people in rural areas are not living the kind of life obtainable in urban areas. The majority of the study participants (219, or 97.33%) strongly disagreed that they are comfortable with the current state of their community, as compared to 210 (93.3%) of the study participants who disagreed with this. Moreover, 99 (44% of the study respondents) strongly agreed with this fact, as compared to 59 (26.22%) who agreed with it. This implies that the study respondents are not comfortable with the current state of their community. The majority of the study participants, 199 (88.4%), strongly agreed that there has been an effort by the government and NGOs to improve infrastructure in their area, while 169 (75.1%) agreed with this fact. On the other hand, 153 (68%) and 88 (39.1%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with and agreed, respectively. This implies that there has been an effort by the government and NGOs to improve infrastructure in their area.

Research Question 2

What is the potency of infrastructural development in attracting the diaspora indigenes back to rural Essien Udim Local Government Area?

Table 2: The potency of infrastructural development in attracting the diaspora indigenes back to rural Essien Udim Local Government Area

S/N	QUESTIONS	SA	A	D	SD
1.	The presence of infrastructure will make my business to thrive.	215 (95.5%)	201 (89.3%)	69 (30.6%)	89 (39.5%)
2.	I will be able to learn skills that will make me employed and employ others if the facilities are accessible.	201 (89.3%)	183 (81.3%)	51 (22.6%)	96 (42.6%)
3.	Will you compete favourably with those in the urban areas if the rural areas are developed?	199 (88.4%)	135 (0.6%)	48 (21.3%)	78 (34.6%)
4.	Has lack of infrastructures made you not to acquire the skills needed to develop your area and also employ yourself and others?	175 (77.7%)	159 (70.6%)	70 (31.1%)	91 (40.4%)

Source: Researcher's fieldwork, 2023

Table 2 shows the opinions of respondents on the potency of infrastructural development in attracting diaspora indigenes back to rural Essien Udim LGA. The majority of the study participants, 215 (95.5%), strongly agreed that the presence of infrastructure will make their businesses thrive, as compared to 201 (89.3%) of the respondents who agreed to this fact. On the other hand, 89 (39.5%) of the respondents strongly disagreed, while 69 (30.6%) disagreed with this fact. This implies that the presence of infrastructure will make their business thrive. The majority of the study participants, 201 (89.3%), strongly agreed that they will be able to learn skills that will make me employed and employ others if the facilities are accessible, as compared to 183 (81.3%), who agreed to this fact. On the other hand, 96 (42.6%) and 51 (22.6%) of the study respondents strongly disagreed with and agreed with this fact. This implies that the respondents will be able to learn skills that will make them employable and also employ others if the facilities are accessible. The majority of the study participants, 199 (88.4%), strongly agreed that they will compete favourably with those in urban areas if the rural areas are developed, as compared to 135 (0.6%) who agreed to this assertion.

Moreover, 78 (34.6%) and 48 (21.3%) strongly disagreed and agreed accordingly. This implies that the respondents will compete favourably with those in the urban areas if the rural areas are developed. The majority of the respondents, 175 (77.7%), strongly agreed that a lack of infrastructure prevents them from acquiring the skills needed to develop the area and also employ themselves and others, as compared to 159 (70.6%) who agreed to this fact. On the other hand, 91 (40.4%) of the study participants strongly disagreed, and 70 (31.1%) disagreed. This implies that a lack of infrastructure prevented them from acquiring the skills needed to develop their area and also employ themselves and others.

Findings of the Study

Findings from the study revealed that rural development can bring back absentee indigenes of Essien Udim local government area. The majority of the study respondents strongly agreed that there has been an effort by government and non-government organisations to improve infrastructure in the area, although the effort has not yielded any results as expected. Findings from the study also revealed that when infrastructure is put in place in rural areas, it will attract diasporic indigenes and people from other cultures back home. This finding corroborates the findings of Anaeto (2003), Uwakah (1995), Ujo (1994), and Akpan (2012), who stated that rural development is a

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multidimensional approach based on a combination of factors such as the right technology, education, access to physical inputs, attractive markets and programmes of agriculture, education, health, rural electrification, and cooperatives, which are essential to reducing the population of urban areas and causing people to migrate to rural areas.

Findings from the study on the potency of infrastructural development in attracting diasporic indigenes back to the rural Essien Udim local government area show that the presence of infrastructure will make businesses thrive. The majority of the study respondents strongly agreed that they will be able to learn skills that will make them employable if the facilities are accessible. These findings give credence to those of Nwaezike (2009), Ujo (1994), Onimode (1981), and Takechi (2001), who contended that discriminatory government policies in favour of urban development, responses to disparities in income, employment, accessibility and ease of communication and transport, and other socioeconomic amenities can predispose a certain rural population to migration.

Conclusion

The study has established that there have been efforts by government agencies and NGOs to develop rural areas, but such efforts have not been sustainable and have not yielded any positive results. This is because, despite promises by different administrations on rural development, it is merely paper work as implementation becomes very difficult and the status of the rural areas remains the same from time to time. Moreso, access to infrastructure, education, and industries will bring absentee and diasporic indigenes of Essien Udim local government area back home. This is the major reason why some of the indigenes who are in diaspora will not return because they feel they will be completely shut out of modern infrastructure that makes life meaningful, that they enjoyed in the urban areas. Today, the presence of infrastructure will create employment for youth, make businesses thrive, and reduce rural-urban migration. If there is a conscious effort in the development of rural areas, the dwellers will compete favourably with those in the urban areas.

Recommendations

In view of the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Local, state, and federal governments should ensure the full participation of

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- members of rural communities and grassroots organisations in the design and implementation of rural development policies and programmes. This will ensure that the programmes are relevant to local needs and in keeping with personal and social values, as well as promote awareness of demographic problems.
- ii. community collaboration and community-based initiative in the formulation and management of rural development programmes in partnership with NGOs and the three tiers of government should be encouraged and strengthened
 - iii. Carrying out periodic surveys to ascertain the rural dwellers' development priorities in order to ensure that they are carried along in the development efforts to better their lives.

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